

SYMPTOMS OF ANXIETY, DEPRESSION, AND STREE IN UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS AT A PUBLIC UNIVERSITY IN INHAMBANE, MOZAMBIQUE.

SINTOMAS DE ANSIEDADE, DEPRESSÃO E ESTRESSE EM ESTUDANTES DE GRADUAÇÃO DE UMA UNIVERSIDADE PÚBLICA EM INHAMBANE - MOÇAMBIQUE

SÍNTOMAS DE ANSIEDAD, DEPRESIÓN Y ESTRÉS EN ESTUDIANTES DE POSGRADO DE UNA UNIVERSIDAD PÚBLICA DE INHAMBANE – MOZAMBIQUE

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Abstract

Studies on mental health in higher education students often point out that this is a population group that is very affected by various mental problems related to their academic experience. However, it was found that, in Mozambique, the area of student mental health has received little attention in research and in institutional student assistance policies. This study aimed to evaluate the symptoms of anxiety, depression and stress in 386 students from various undergraduate courses at a public university, located in Inhambane - Mozambique. To this end, cross-sectional, descriptive and quantitative research was developed, applying the sociodemographic and academic data questionnaire and the Anxiety, Depression and Stress Scale (EADS-21). Descriptive analyzes (means, standard deviation and frequencies) and Cronbach's alpha were performed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences, version 22 and Jamovi, version 2.5. The results revealed that most investigated students present symptoms in the dimensions of stress and anxiety. Among the phenomena investigated, the most frequent in the sample was stress. Faced with this emerging reality, the implementation

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of policies to care for students' mental health and carrying out research on the social determinants of mental suffering are necessary, pertinent and urgent actions.

Keywords: Higher education; Student; Mental health.

Resumo

Estudos sobre saúde mental em estudantes do ensino superior apontam frequentemente que este é um grupo populacional muito acometido por diversos problemas mentais relacionados à sua vivência acadêmica. No entanto, verificou-se que, em Moçambique a área de saúde mental de estudantes tem recebido pouca atenção na pesquisa e nas políticas institucionais de assistência estudantil. Este estudo objetivou avaliar os sintomas de ansiedade, depressão e estresse em 386 estudantes de diversos cursos de graduação de uma Universidade pública, situada em Inhambane - Moçambique. Para tal, desenvolveu-se uma pesquisa transversal, descritiva e quantitativa, aplicando o questionário de dados sociodemográficos e acadêmicos e, a Escala de Ansiedade, Depressão e Estresse (EADS-21). Foram feitas análises descritivas (médias, desvio-padrão e frequências) e alpha de Cronbach através do *Statistical Package for the Social Sciences*, versão 22 e Jamovi, versão 2.5. Os resultados revelaram que a maioria dos estudantes investigados apresentou sintomas nas dimensões de estresse e de ansiedade. Dentre os fenômenos pesquisados, o mais frequente na amostra foi o estresse. Diante dessa realidade descortinada, a implantação de políticas de atenção à saúde mental de estudantes e a realização de pesquisas sobre determinantes sociais do sofrimento mental são ações necessárias, pertinentes e urgentes.

Palavras-chave: Ensino superior; Estudante; Saúde mental.

Resumen

Los estudios sobre salud mental en estudiantes de educación superior suelen señalar que se trata de un grupo poblacional muy afectado por diversos problemas mentales relacionados con su experiencia académica. Sin embargo, se constató que, en Mozambique, el área de la salud mental de los estudiantes ha recibido poca atención en las investigaciones y en las políticas institucionales de asistencia estudiantil. Este estudio tuvo como objetivo evaluar los síntomas de ansiedad, depresión y estrés en 386 estudiantes de diversos cursos de pregrado de una universidad pública, ubicada en Inhambane - Mozambique. Para ello se desarrolló una investigación transversal, descriptiva y cuantitativa, aplicando el cuestionario de datos sociodemográficos y académicos y la Escala de Ansiedad, Depresión y Estrés (EADS-21). Los análisis descriptivos (medias, desviación estándar y frecuencias) y alfa de Cronbach se realizaron mediante el Paquete Estadístico para Ciencias Sociales, versión 22 y Jamovi, versión 2.5. Los resultados revelaron que la mayoría de los estudiantes investigados presentaron síntomas en las dimensiones de estrés y ansiedad. Entre los fenómenos investigados, el más frecuente en la muestra fue el estrés. Ante esta realidad emergente, la implementación de políticas para el cuidado de la salud mental de los estudiantes y la realización de investigaciones sobre los determinantes sociales del sufrimiento mental son acciones necesarias, pertinentes y urgentes.

Palabras clave: Educación superior; Alumno; Salud mental.

Introduction

Universities play a significant role in training professionals, disseminating science, culture and citizenship, research, innovation and outreach, which places them in a position to be a determining vector in ensuring that development policies and strategies have the technical support for their management, implementation and monitoring (Valá, 2016). In this context, universities are considered central to ensuring that the country's development agenda is adequately fulfilled, respecting the required technical and scientific standards, whether in the economic, environmental and engineering fields, or in the domains of education, health, water, agriculture, energy, international relations, tourism and transport.

Additionally, higher education is where highly qualified professionals, researchers, and teachers are trained in various fields. Considering these and other roles and functions that universities perform, promoting the expansion and equitable access to higher education, ensuring national and international quality standards, is an emerging challenge for many countries, especially developing ones like Mozambique.

In the national context, Decree n° 61/2022, of November 23, which creates The National Qualifications Framework, abbreviated as QNQ, determines that at the academic and/or professional graduation level, the student possesses knowledge of a recognized discipline and mastery of ideas, principles, concepts, and technical-scientific research methods in problem-solving. Likewise, the student is expected to be able to critically discern the principles, theories, research methodologies, and current literature of the discipline.

Regarding skills and abilities, the decree stipulates that graduates must demonstrate the capacity for independent reasoning and effective communication in solving concrete problems. And around autonomy and responsibility, graduates are expected to conceive and manage processes and tasks, establish goals, and ensure their achievement at both individual and group levels.

Regarding expansion, in the past 20 years, Higher Education (HE) in Mozambique has registered substantial growth in terms of the number of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and students. This progress has been justified by the opening of new

HEIs during this period, which increased from 10 in 2003 (Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Technology [MESCT], 2004) to 56 in 2023 (Ministry of Science, Technology and Higher Education [MCTES], 2023). During the same period, there was a considerable increase in the number of students who enrolled in these HEIs, from 17,225 (MESCT, 2004) to 237,777 students (MCTES, 2023).

However, the current higher education student population in the country corresponds to a rate of 8% of the group of Mozambicans of higher education age (gross enrollment rate in higher education) (MCTES, 2023). As can be seen, despite this significant progress, the gross enrollment rate in higher education in the country remains low, relative to the average gross rate in Southern Africa and other contexts close to the country's reality, becoming an increasingly pressing challenge due to the high demographic growth of the Mozambican population, with emphasis on young people (MCTES, 2023).

Challenges also persist regarding different forms of equity (Mandlate; Nivagara, 2019), that is, from the point of view of regional and provincial distribution of HEIs, investment and course offerings, which in some cases limits easy access to these institutions. In other words, most HEIs are in the southern region of the country and/or in the three major cities, namely: Maputo, Nampula and Beira.

Similarly, the MCTES (2023) recognized that the higher education student population was disproportionately distributed across the different regions and provinces of the country, with the city of Maputo having the highest concentration of students, estimated at 100,883 (42.4%), with new enrollment and graduation rates of 34.5% and 29.7%, respectively. This was followed by the provinces of Nampula with 23,828 (10%) and Sofala with 23,402 (9.8%), successively representing the second and third provinces with the highest number of students. Conversely, the province of Niassa had the lowest number of higher education students, with 7,473 (3.1%).

Of the total university population, 57% studied in public higher education institutions (HEIs), despite these representing only 39%, or 22 out of the 56 existing in Mozambique (MCTES, 2023). This occurs because, from a comparative cost-of-training perspective, they are considered more accessible, leading to fierce competition for

places and/or certain courses offered in some of these institutions. In this sense, being admitted to a public HEI in Mozambique constitutes a great victory and a source of joy, happiness, and fulfillment for both the student and their family. However, these positive feelings developed upon admission and entry into HEIs can turn negative due to the various challenges and demands inherent in academic training.

Thus, research on adaptation, academic satisfaction, and mental health of students in higher education demonstrates that their entry into and retention in higher education institutions can constitute a huge challenge for some, especially those who move from rural to urban areas, where these institutions are located. As Silva and Ximenes (2022a, p. 68) point out in their study on the psychosocial implications of rural-urban migration for young university students, "the lifestyle of young university students who experience rural-urban migration is fraught with numerous challenges, including a scarcity of financial resources." Additionally, these authors highlighted dilemmas arising from migration for these traveling university students, which are reflected in changes in socialization patterns, distancing from family ties, and cultural shifts.

This scenario can be more critical for some higher education students in Mozambique, a multicultural and multilingual country with approximately 20 different national languages (Ministry of Education and Human Development [MINEDH], 2023), which can hinder the socialization process and generate social and linguistic isolation (Maússe *et al.*, 2024). Furthermore, most Mozambican higher education institutions lack public student assistance policies (Mechisso, 2017) and do not offer psychosocial support services (Sunde, 2022, 2023). Furthermore, Mozambican public HEIs have been experiencing serious problems with public investment and funding since 2016 (Bonde; Matavel, 2022), due, on the one hand, to the paralysis of external support from donors, as a consequence of the discovery of public debt that was not approved by the Assembly of the Republic, commonly known as hidden debts, as well as the financial and economic crisis that plagues the country, which limits the provision of material conditions.

This scenario, coupled with the various challenges of the university environment itself (e.g., problems with academic adaptation, difficulties in understanding the subject matter, a greater number of subjects, new subjects, new study and teaching strategies,

interpersonal relationship problems, and academic overload) (Abacar; Aliante; António, 2021 ; Cristo *et al.* , 2019 ; Ghizoni; Silva; Santos, 2024 ; Nhachengo; Almeida, 2020, 2021 ; Rodrigues; Correa, 2022), can contribute to the breakdown of initial expectations, create performance, learning, and satisfaction problems, and lead to thoughts of intention and/or abandonment (Almeida; Araújo; Martins, 2016 ; Carlotto; Câmara, 2022).

The persistence or chronicity of difficulties experienced during academic life can trigger a series of emotional and psychological changes in students, such as anxiety, depression, stress, *burnout* , and other mental disorders (Alqurashi *et al.* , 2022 ; Fragelli; Fragelli, 2021 ; Gómez-Urquiza *et al.* , 2023 ; Lambert; Castro, 2020 ; Meneses; Santos, 2023 ; Pedrelli *et al.* , 2015 ; Rosales-Ricardo *et al.* , 202). Because not all students have the necessary resources to deal with the emotional and situational issues experienced during their undergraduate studies (Souza; Murgo; Barros, 2021), and not all higher education institutions offer assistance and support services for students' psychological needs (Gaiotto *et al.* , 2021; Oliveira; Carmo; Vêras, 2023; Romanini; Gumucio, 2023).

Given this scenario, research conducted internationally in recent decades on the psychological vulnerability of students experiencing higher education indicates high levels of psychological distress in this population group, with an increased prevalence of several mental health problems mentioned above (Ariño *et al.* , 2023; Barros; Peixoto, 2023; Silva; Ximenes, 2022b). Thus, empirical investigations carried out with students from higher education institutions in various countries around the world have similarly revealed the occurrence of high rates of mental health problems, such as anxiety, depression, and stress.

Internationally, several investigations have been carried out in certain countries using different instruments to assess anxiety, depression, and stress in university students, for example in China (Shi *et al.* , 2016), Portugal (Gonçalves; Santos; Silva, 2023 ; Simões *et al.* , 2024), Colombia (Restrepo; Quirama; Cruz, 2022), and Brazil (Aguiar *et al.* , 2023 ; Costa). *et al.* , 2020; Leão *et al.* , 2018), In Namibia (Mhata *et al.* , 2023) percentages ranging from 13.10% to 76.21% of participants were reported. Additionally, some systematic review and meta-analysis studies report concerning prevalences of the constructs in question (Demenech *et al.* , 2021; Li *et al.* , 2022; Mao *et al.* , 2019).

For illustrative purposes, the study by Demenech *et al.* (2021) on the prevalence of anxiety and depression in Brazilian university students indicated that it was successively estimated at 37.75% and 28.51%. In turn, Li *et al.* (2022) assessed the prevalence of depression and anxiety in university students globally and potential associated factors. The results indicated that the prevalence of symptoms of depression and anxiety in this population worldwide was 33.6% and 39%, respectively. High prevalence rates of depression in students were found in Africa, at 40.1%, and in low-income countries such as Mozambique, at 42.5%.

In Mozambique, there has been some progress, albeit in its early stages, in research on psychological vulnerability among university students. For example, Aliante *et al.* (2019) assessed stress symptomatology. In 176 undergraduate students from a public university in Nampula, in the northern region of the country, using the Lipp Stress Symptoms Inventory for Adults (ISSL), the results revealed that 154 (87.5%) participants presented stress symptoms, of which 112 (63.6%) were in the resistance phase, 33 (18.75%) in the alarm phase, and nine (5.15%) in the exhaustion phase, with symptomatology predominantly of a psychological nature. Using the same inventory, Matsinhe *et al.* (2020) investigated stress symptomatology in 100 undergraduate psychology students at a public university in Maputo, in the south of the country. The results suggested that 55% of the students involved showed signs of stress, with 40% in the resistance phase, 13% in the exhaustion phase, and 2% in the alarm phase, with a predominance of symptoms of a psychological nature.

As observed in the studies presented, despite their different contexts and methodologies, they converge on the fact that university students are affected by various types of mental health problems and require proper care, assistance, and monitoring (Barros; Peixoto, 2023; Brandolin *et al.*, 2023; Romanini; Gumucio, 2023). However, in Mozambique, mental health is poorly investigated, and its care is largely neglected within the context of institutional public policies for student assistance (Cassambai; Aliante, 2020; Sunde, 2023).

Furthermore, it is our understanding, through the reviewed literature, that the studies existing so far in Mozambique have been mostly conducted in Nampula, in the northern region, which suggests their expansion to other contexts, such as the central

and southern regions of the country. The undertaking of this investigation is also justified by the recent cases of suicides and attempted suicides among students on two *campuses* of the university under investigation.

Considering the importance of knowing the prevalence rates of mental disorders and understanding their predictors in university students in order to better intervene with effective mental health care actions in this target group (Fragelli; Fragelli, 2021 ; Lomba; Pan, 2021 ; Rodrigues; Correa, 2022), the results of this investigation provide scientific indicators of the emotional and psychological states of students, revealing an invisible reality of mental suffering in this target group at the investigated public university. At the same time, they can provide a basis for urgent action in designing and implementing a mental health care policy for students at the university in question.

Finally, the results obtained constitute a scientific contribution to the limited existing literature in Mozambique on this subject and open avenues for future research, suggesting the development of investigations on the topic in other universities, on psychosocial risk factors, as well as the need to implement intervention actions in this area. Considering the above, the present study aimed to evaluate the symptoms of anxiety, depression, and stress in students at a public university located in Inhambane, Mozambique.

Methods

This section explains the method used to conduct this research. It describes the type of research, the procedures, and the data collection and analysis techniques.

- Type of search

It is known that there are several criteria for classifying research. The choice of one set of these criteria varies depending on the phenomenon studied and the data collection and analysis techniques required. In this context, this research is classified as quantitative, cross-sectional, and descriptive. It is quantitative and descriptive due to

the use of standardized instruments in the data collection process, as well as descriptive statistical analyses (Gil, 2020; Prodanov; Freitas, 2013), duly explained in the sections on data collection instruments and data analysis techniques that follow. The cross-sectional design was due to its purpose of evaluating and understanding the symptomatology of anxiety, depression, and stress in university students, which occurred in a static way, describing this given reality at a single point in time (Marin *et al.*, 2021)

- Data collection instruments

Data collection was carried out through the application of two self-report questionnaires, namely: the sociodemographic and academic data questionnaire and the Portuguese language version of the *Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scales* (DASS-21). The first questionnaire was intended to obtain personal information, such as: gender, age, marital status, course, type of education and year of attendance. This data was used to characterize the participating students.

The DASS-21 was developed by Lovibond and Lovibond (1995). The scale was translated, adapted and validated for Portuguese in Portugal (Apóstolo; Mendes; Azeredo, 2006; Pais-Ribeiro; Honrado; Leal, 2004) and Brazil (Vignola; Tucci, 2014). The DASS-21 presents items that report symptoms of three constructs: anxiety, depression, and stress. The anxiety subscale assesses persistent states of anxiety and irritability, as well as intense responses of perceived panic and fear; the depression dimension assesses loss of... Self-esteem, demotivation, discouragement, and apathy. Finally, the stress subscale assesses symptoms of impatience and irritability, low tolerance for frustration, and difficulty relaxing (Barros; Sacau-Fontenla, 2022).

The DASS-21 is an instrument in which each respondent indicates the severity and/or frequency with which the statement occurred in the last month and structurally presents three dimensions: Depression (items: 3, 5, 10, 13, 16, 17 and 21), Anxiety (items: 2, 4, 7, 9, 15, 19 and 20) and Stress. (items: 1, 6, 8, 11, 12, 14 and 18). The response format is a 4-point *Likert scale* (0 – did not apply to me at all, 1 – applied to me sometimes, 2 –

applied to me often, and 3 – applied to me most of the time). Higher scores on the DASS-21 (examples: 2 and 3) correspond to higher levels of anxiety, depression, and stress.

The preference for the DASS-21 as a data collection instrument in this research is justified by several reasons, such as not requiring the payment of copyright fees, i.e., being free to use for research purposes: having versions in Portuguese, having few items, and being easy to administer. Additionally, the Portuguese version used in this research showed good indicators of internal reliability with *Cronbach's alpha* (α) values greater than 0.70 (Pais-Ribeiro; Honrado; Leal, 2004; Vignola; Tucci, 2014).

In the present study, the overall α value was 0.885 and the Omega value was 0.886. All dimensions of the instrument achieved indices above 0.70; $\alpha = 0.78$ and Omega = 0.80 for depression, $\alpha = 0.71$ and Omega = 0.72 for stress, and $\alpha = 0.70$ and Omega = 0.71 for anxiety (see Table 2). Furthermore, this measure involves a theoretical model that accurately discriminates between symptoms of anxiety and depression, which are not always differentiated by other scales or instruments (Lovibond; Lovibond, 1995; Pais-Ribeiro; Honrado; Leal, 2004).

- Ethical procedures and precautions

Data collection took place in October 2022. Questionnaires were administered in classrooms during school days. The data collection process was preceded by a request for and authorization to conduct the research from the Extension Directorate of Massinga, Save University (Universidade Save – UniSave in Portuguese language), located in Massinga, Inhambane province, in southern Mozambique.

UniSave is a public higher education institution created through Decree n°6/2019, of February 15, within the framework of the restructuring of the Pedagogical University and Higher Education in Mozambique, in order to provide Public Universities with more efficient administration and management mechanisms capable of responding effectively to the current dynamics of the country. Thus, UniSave is a public higher education institution with statutory, regulatory, scientific, pedagogical, patrimonial,

disciplinary, administrative and financial autonomy, responsible for offering specialized training at the higher education level in the country with a view to pursuing its defined mission and vision (UniSave, 2023).

Currently, UniSave is structured into seven faculties and one higher school: Faculty of Education and Psychology (FACEP), Faculty of Natural and Exact Sciences (FCNE), Faculty of Arts and Social Sciences (FLCS), Faculty of Health and Sports Sciences (FCSD), Faculty of Economics and Administration (FEA), Faculty of Engineering (FE), Faculty of Veterinary Medicine and Zootechnics (FMVZ) and Higher School of Agricultural Sciences (ESCA) (UniSave, 2023).

The organic units are the institutional, pedagogical, and scientific or extension-related foundation through which UniSave carries out its mission and responsibilities. UniSave's organic units are subdivided into territorial or geographic units (extensions), academic units (higher institutes, colleges, faculties, and Distance Learning Centers), and research and extension units (research centers, Professional Training Centers).

UniSave has its headquarters in Chongoene, Gaza province, and two extensions in Inhambane, namely: Maxixe Extension and Massinga Extension. This study was developed in the Massinga Extension. According to data from the 2017 General Population and Housing Census, the province of Inhambane has an area of 68,615 km² and a population of 1,454,804, the majority of whom were female (n = 789,564 inhabitants) (National Institute of Statistics, 2019). Administratively, Inhambane has 14 districts and cities, namely: Inhambane City (capital), Funhalouro, Govuro, Homoíne, Inharrime, Inhassoro, Jangamo, Mabote, Massinga, Maxixe City, Morrumbene, Panda, Vilankulo, and Zavala.

During the questionnaire completion process, the researchers previously explained the objectives, methodology, and relevance of the research. Following this, the researchers requested the voluntary participation of students, and those who verbally consented were given printed questionnaires to complete. Anonymity and confidentiality of the information collected were guaranteed.

Regarding the dissemination and feedback of the results, these were presented in October 2023 at the IV International Seminar on Scientific Research and the 14th National Seminar on the Dissemination of Results of Projects Funded by the National

Research Fund (FNI), which took place between the 19th and 20th. A public presentation of the results was also made at the research institution in October 2024 on World Mental Health Day. The university meeting was attended by students, professors, technical-administrative staff, hierarchical superiors of the institution, and other interested parties.

- Data analysis

The data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), version 22, and Jamovi, version 2.5. In this study, only simple statistical analyses (absolute and percentage frequencies) were performed for each item and factor of the DASS-21 and sociodemographic variables. Similarly, internal reliability was inspected by calculating *Cronbach's alpha* and *McDonald's Omega* for the three dimensions and the DASS-21.

According to Gonçalves (2014), the symptoms of depression, anxiety, and stress as a function of the DASS-21 are psychological disturbances conceptualized and evaluated in dimensional rather than categorical terms; that is, they are essentially differences in degree (normal subjects versus subjects with psychological disturbance) ranging from "normal" to "very severe." Thus, to determine the phenomena with the highest predominance of symptoms of anxiety, depression, and stress... Among the students surveyed, the sum of the frequencies of each item in scores 2 and 3 of the DASS-21 was considered.

Results and discussion

This section presents and discusses the results of this investigation. First, the participating students are characterized, followed by a description of the symptoms of depression, anxiety, and stress in the sample studied, as well as their respective discussion.

- Characterization of the participants

As illustrated in Table 1, this research involved a non-probabilistic accessibility sample of 386 university students, aged between 17 and 42 years ($M = 24.6$), duly enrolled in 2022 at a public university located in the province of Inhambane, southern Mozambique. Of the total sample, 242 (62.7%) were female students, and 295 (76.4%) attended the daytime course.

This research involved students from 12 undergraduate courses, namely: 92 (23.8%) from Biology, 36 (9.3%) from Educational Psychology and the same number from Agriculture, 33 (8.5%) from Chemistry, 28 (7.3%) from Physics and History, 27 (7%) from Human Resources, 26 (6.7%) from Psychology, 23 (5.9%) from Basic Education and 22 (5.7%), 18 (4.7%) and 17 (4.4%) from Environment and Community Sustainability, Public and Local Government Management and Geography, respectively. Most of the students in this study ($n = 166$; 44%) were in the 4th year, followed by those in the 1st year ($n = 114$; 29.5%), the 3rd year ($n = 54$; 14%), and the 2nd year ($n = 52$; 13.5%).

Table 1 – Sociodemographic and academic profile of the study participants

VARIABLE		N	%
Gender	Masculine	144	37.3
	Feminine	242	62.7
	Total	386	100
Ages	From 17 to 25 years old	255	66.1
	From 26 to 35 years old	84	21.8
	36 years and older	47	12.2
Frequency course	Basic Education	23	9.6
	Educational Psychology	36	5.9
	Psychology	26	6.7
	Geography	17	4.4
	History	28	7.3
	Human Resources Management	27	7.0
	Physical	28	7.3
	Agriculture	36	9.3
	Public and Local Government Management	18	4.7
	Environment and Community Sustainability	22	5.7
	Chemical	33	8.5
	Biology	92	23.8
Year of attendance	First year	114	29.5
	Second year	52	13.5
	Third year	54	14.0
	Fourth year	166	43.0
Class attendance schedule	Labor	295	76.4
	After-work	91	23.6

Source: Author's own work.

- Symptoms of depression, anxiety, and stress in investigated students

Regarding the frequency of symptoms across the three constructs investigated, the results in Table 2 indicate that the majority of students surveyed reported symptoms related to stress and anxiety. However, the frequency of symptoms recorded in the depression subscale cannot be ignored.

Table 2 – Frequency of symptoms of anxiety, depression, and stress in university students surveyed

Factor	Items	N (%)				Prevalence*
		0	1	2	3	
Depression $\alpha = 0.78$ and Omega = 0.80	Item 3	195(50.5)	108(28,0)	47(12,2)	36(9,3)	83 (21.5)
	Item 5	102(26,4)	154(39,9)	71(18,4)	59(15,3)	130 (33.6)
	Item 10	236(61,1)	80(20,7)	34(8,8)	36(9,3)	70 (18.1)
	Item 13	111(28,8)	140(36,3)	80(20,7)	55(14,2)	135 (34.9)
	Item 16	203(52,6)	116(30,1)	44(11,4)	23(6,0)	67 (17.3)
	Item 17	219(56,7)	79(20.5)	48(12,4)	40(10,4)	88 (22.7)
	Item 21	215(55,7)	79(20.5)	35(9,1)	57(14,8)	92 (23.8)
Anxiety $\alpha = 0.70$ and Omega = 0.71	Item 2	224(58,0)	87(22.5)	54(14,0)	21(5,4)	75 (19.4)
	Item 4	266(68,9)	74(19,4)	23(6,0)	23(6,0)	46 (11.9)
	Item 7	212(54,9)	98(25,4)	47(12,2)	29(7,5)	76 (19.6)
	Item 9	190(49,2)	98(25,4)	58(15,0)	40(10,4)	98 (25.3)
	Item 15	179(46,4)	123(31,9)	51(13,2)	33(8,5)	84 (21.7)
	Item 19	121(31,3)	115(29,8)	68(17,9)	81(21,0)	149 (38.6)
	Item 20	153(53,6)	109(28,2)	69(17,9)	55(14,2)	124 (32.1)
Stress $\alpha = 0.71$ and Omega = 0.72	Item 1	178(46,1)	141(36.5)	46(11,9)	21(5,4)	67 (17.3)
	Item 6	132(34,2)	146(37,8)	75(19,4)	33(8,5)	108 (27.9)
	Item 8	113(29,3)	124(32,1)	81(21,0)	68(17,6)	149 (38.8)
	Item 11	193(50,0)	136(35,2)	30(7,8)	27(7,0)	57 (14.7)
	Item 12	111(28,8)	157(40,7)	68(17,6)	50(13,0)	118 (30.5)
	Item 14	130(33,7)	133(34,5)	62(16,1)	61(15,1)	123 (31.8)
	Item 18	66(17,1)	158(40,9)	88(22,8)	74(19,2)	162 (41.9)

Source: Author's own work. ***Note:** This is the sum of the frequencies of items 2 and 3.

According to Table 2, in the stress subscale, the most frequently reported symptoms were: emotional sensitivity, nervousness, a feeling of intolerance towards events that prevented finishing what was being done, difficulty relaxing, and a tendency to overreact in certain situations. In the anxiety factor, the following symptoms were more frequent: changes in heart rate without physical exercise, sudden frights without

apparent reason, and excessive worry about situations that could trigger panic. Finally, in the depression dimension, the most evident symptoms were characterized by feelings of discouragement and pessimism, and difficulty taking initiative to do things.

Regarding the overall levels of anxiety, depression, and stress, the results in Table 2 reveal that most of the students investigated presented severe to extremely severe symptoms in the dimensions of stress and anxiety. Hypothetically, the symptomatology identified in this study may be associated with several factors, such as the data collection period, university characteristics – lack of effective student support and assistance policies – and socioeconomic factors in the country.

Regarding the data collection period, it is important to remember that it took place in October 2022. According to the academic calendar of the university investigated, classes for the second semester begin in mid-July and end in early November. In this context, the month of October has been characterized by the completion of various tasks and activities, such as assessments and seminar presentations, which, in a way, can generate anxiety and stress related to tests and the fear of failure, which will culminate in failing the courses in progress.

It is also worth remembering that the data collection took place a year after the end of the quarantine/state of emergency in Mozambique and the return to in-person activities, through Decree n° 14/2022, of April 20. Despite this, in October 2022, many people were still living in uncertainty and fear of contamination by the pandemic virus, both within the university environment and outside of it, since the institution and the places of mobility have poor hygiene conditions (Aliante; Taria; José, 2023). In this context, the return to in-person classes under the described conditions could be perceived as a situation of danger, fear, and uncertainty, potentially leading to psychological strain, with tendencies towards possible suffering and mental illness in students (Moronte, 2020).

Ribeiro and Ribeiro (2023) argue that with the emergence of Covid-19, new modes of subjectivation arose as a result of the pandemic in coping with the imposed reality and the worsening of people's mental health. Similarly, Pires, Monteiro, and Gregoviski (2023) maintain that the pandemic increased psychosocial impacts and

required even more adjustments from these students after the continuation of activities remotely and with the imposed social distancing. This current scenario has raised awareness of mental health issues, given the potentiation of symptoms already experienced by undergraduates. It is also understood that the repercussions of the pandemic will last for a long period. Furthermore, in addition to this, the fear of contracting disease, anguish, grief, insecurity about the future, isolation, and daily changes in their work and personal activities caused constant worry.

In parallel, Wang and Liu (2022), in developing a systematic review and meta-analysis on the prevalence of anxiety symptoms among Chinese university students during the COVID-19 pandemic, found that the combined prevalence of anxiety symptoms was 25.0% (95% CI: 21%–29%, $p < 0.001$). Furthermore, in the later stages of the COVID-19 pandemic, compared to the initial stages, the prevalence of anxiety was higher (29.1% vs. 17.2%). Based on these findings, these authors suggested that it was necessary to provide ongoing psychological assessment and treatment services for university students.

Regarding the characteristics of the university studied, although it has a Social Services sector, this sector is exclusively dedicated to the management of scholarships and obituaries. Therefore, students facing difficulties adapting to the return to in-person classes, insecurity, and fear of the post-pandemic effects did not receive any support or psychosocial assistance from the university. However, Veiga and Lopes (2020) argue that the university's role cannot be limited to the academic calendar but must extend to people's lives and the different contexts in which they participate and for which they are co-responsible. In this context, universities should provide psychological support services to facilitate this process for students and contribute to resolving difficulties in the personal, social, academic, and vocational domains.

Similarly, at the time of data collection for this study, the *campus* under investigation faced several infrastructure-related difficulties. In light of this, the UniSave Strategic Plan 2023-2030 points to the following as some of the weaknesses: the lack of provision of psycho-pedagogical and social support for students, the absence of a functional data network (*internet*), the glaring lack of laboratory equipment in sufficient

quantity and quality to cover all practical disciplines of the courses and to satisfy students, and the lack of an updated and/or insufficient bibliographic collection. (UniSave, 2023). These conditions can be assessed as academic difficulties and stressors.

Regarding the country's socioeconomic issues, it is important to highlight that, since a large part of the Mozambican population lives from informal work, such as stalls, bars, markets, artisanal fishing, and subsistence agriculture (Batone, 2020), Covid-19 resulted in job losses and/or a reduction in sales and income levels. Similarly, the *Doing Business Mozambique 2019* report describes that a large part of the private sector in the country remains informal. Approximately 40% of the country's Gross Domestic Product is currently produced in the informal economy, and people working in this informal sector do not have access to legal protection, social security, and pensions (World Bank, 2019). This scenario may have impacted the reduction in the allowance received by students to cover their academic expenses, leading to constant worry.

Furthermore, Mozambique is a country that has been experiencing an economic and financial crisis since 2015, which was exacerbated by Covid-19, leading to an increase in the cost of living for the population. From the perspective of the United Nations Development Program (UNDP, 2022, p. 7), “the impacts of the Covid-19 pandemic on economies are insignificant when compared to the expected upheavals caused by the power of new technologies and the dangers and transformations they represent.” It is also emphasized that the financial crisis can be a significant factor in the deterioration of people's mental health.

Mozambique is one of the countries with a low Human Development Index (HDI), assessed at 0.44 in 2022 (UNDP, 2022), placing it in 6th position among the poorest nations in the world, according to the UNDP's 2021/2022 HDI report. According to this entity, low-income people, especially those struggling to meet basic needs such as rent and food, suffered disproportionately in several countries during the pandemic period (UNDP, 2022).

UNDP (2022) also points out that stressors do not need to reach the level of globalized trauma to cause mental distress. In fact, one of the most serious economic threats to people's mental well-being seems to result from repeated financial shocks,

such as loss of income, especially for poor people and men. Economic insecurity – or even just the perception of such insecurity, however temporary – is an important factor.

Specifically, regarding university students, Ghizoni, Silva and Santos (2024) and Soares (2024) argue that the specific challenges they face during academic life, such as academic pressure, social isolation, and financial worries, have negative repercussions on students' mental health and well-being.

The results of this study corroborate those of previous research that used the Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scale (DASS-21) as a data collection instrument. For example, in Brazil, Moutinho *et al.* (2017) investigated the prevalence of depression, anxiety, and stress in 761 students. As a result, 47.1%, 37.2%, and 34.6% reported symptoms of stress, anxiety, and depression, respectively. In Galvão *et al.* (2017), most students (53.8% of the 158 investigated) demonstrated poor sleep quality, presenting levels of stress, anxiety, and depression. superior to the rest.

In turn, Zancan *et al.* (2021) examined the prevalence of stress, anxiety, and depression in a sample of 574 undergraduate and graduate students from Rio Grande. From the South. Of the total, 357 were undergraduates and 217 were postgraduates; stress, anxiety, and depression levels were considered high in this sample.

Barbosa (2021) assessed emotional states in 36 university students using the instrument employed in this research. He found that the stress domain had the highest score, followed by the depression and anxiety domain, partially corroborating the findings of this investigation.

Cristo (2023) evaluated the symptomatology of depression, anxiety, and stress in 92 freshmen from the Physiotherapy, Psychology, and Nutrition courses at a public college. It was found that 35.90% reported symptoms of stress, 26.10% of depression, and 22.80% of anxiety. Similarly, research involving 266 dentistry students from a private college in northern Minas Gerais (Gonçalves; Rebelo; Oliveira, 2023) concluded that moderate to very severe stress was present in 37.2%, anxiety in 47.4%, and depression in 32.7% of the students.

In Portugal, Certo (2016), using a convenience sample of 358 student's representative of the Polytechnic Institute of Bragança, assessed levels of stress, anxiety, and depression. The results showed disparate levels in the three phenomena, with stress being the most significant.

In Mozambique, the results of the research by Alpaca *et al.* (2022) with 105 university students in Nampula point in the same direction. Thus, the results indicated that the stress dimension The most reported symptoms were difficulty relaxing, a tendency to overreact to situations, feeling overly sensitive, and nervousness.

However, in Rufato's study (2023), it was identified that more than 50% of the 829 Brazilian university students presented severe or extremely severe symptoms of anxiety and depression. Stress was the phenomenon with the lowest prevalence of symptoms among the students investigated, which differs from the findings of this study. Similarly, in Iraq, Alhilali, Husni, and Almarabheh (2024), applying the same EADS-21 instrument, found high levels of depression, anxiety, and stress in 74.1%, 90.4%, and 98% of the 140 students, respectively.

Considering that mental health among university students is a significant international public health concern, requiring epidemiological data (Liyanage *et al.*, 2022), this study contributes in this direction by providing information on the symptomatology of anxiety, depression, and stress in a group of students during a given period, allowing for a comparison of the data with international studies to identify regional differences. At the national level, the results of this study are scientific indicators to support area 8 – mental health, trauma, and violence of the Human Health Research Agenda 2024-2028, which includes mental health as one of its priorities (Ministry of Health, 2023).

Furthermore, they can serve to assess the achievement of Goal 3 – ensuring healthy lives and promoting well-being for all at all ages, which includes mental health and well-being in target 3.4 (National Institute of Statistics, 2020) – at the university investigated. Moreover, the results of this study reveal an existing and worrying reality; however, it is rendered invisible in the context of Mozambican Higher Education Institutions due to the scarcity of research in this area and the lack of institutional

policies addressing mental health. Thus, this research contributes to increasing the already limited existing literature on the mental health of university students in the country.

Finally, the study opens avenues and calls for the continued development of further research that will not be limited to investigating the symptomatology of anxiety, depression, and stress, but also the social, academic, cultural, and political determinants of the occurrence of suffering and mental illness in students. This information will be necessary to define and implement actions to promote and intervene in mental health in the university context, aiming to ensure the well-being and quality of life of students, through improved training of mental health professionals based on the most prevalent symptoms in the students investigated, as well as to foster the design and implementation of student assistance policies that include psychosocial support, to offer psychological support programs based on scientific evidence.

Final considerations

This study aimed to evaluate the symptomatology of anxiety, depression, and stress in a sample of students from a public university located in Inhambane, southern Mozambique. Based on the results obtained, a greater predominance of symptoms of stress and anxiety was observed, which may be compromising the mental health and well-being of the students investigated. These findings suggest the need for actions to promote mental health, prevention, and intervention aimed at improving the quality of life and ensuring the psychological well-being of the academic community.

It should be noted that this research is cross-sectional and was conducted at a public higher education institution, which suggests that its results are not generalizable. Even so, it adds to the scarce literature on the mental health of university students in Mozambique and presents indicators of the emotional and psychological state of a group of students. In other words, this study brings to light the symptomatology of mental health problems that affect millions of people, contributing important data to the academic community and to public policy.

Given this, it is pertinent to develop cross-sectional and longitudinal research both in other extensions of the university under study, as well as in other Higher Education Institutions in the country, for a deeper and more unique understanding. Such research should go beyond evaluating the symptomatology of anxiety, stress, and depression, but also explore the social determinants of mental suffering and other mental health problems in students, as well as proposed intervention mechanisms. It is also desirable to investigate the influence of mental health status on the quality of life and academic performance of students.

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